

Short communication

First record of *Plesionoma capeneri* Duarte Rodrigues, 1982 (Heteroptera: Tingidae: Phatnominae) from Madagascar

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Abstract. *Plesionoma capeneri* Duarte Rodrigues, 1982 is reported from Madagascar for the first time. It is also the first record of the genus *Plesionoma* Drake, 1950 from this island.

Key words: Heteroptera, Tingidae, Phatnominae, *Plesionoma capeneri*, distribution, first record, Afrotropical Region, Madagascar.

Madagascan lace bugs of the subfamily Phatnominae were previously represented by two species, namely *Gonycentrum heissi* B. Lis, 2006, and *Phatnoma hova* Schutteden, 1957 (Duarte Rodrigues 1992; Göllner-Scheiding 2004; Lis 2006). In the present note, *Plesionoma capeneri* Duarte Rodrigues, 1982 is reported as the third member of the subfamily Phatnominae from Madagascar.

The species of the genus *Plesionoma* Drake, 1950 are exclusively Afrotropic in distribution (Froeschner 1996; Göllner-Scheiding 2004). Of the five species of the genus described so far, four occur in South Africa, namely *P. biseriatum* Duarte Rodrigues, 1987, *P. capeneri* Duarte Rodrigues, 1982, *P. humeralis* (Distant 1902) and *P. theroni* Duarte Rodrigues, 1988 (Göllner-Scheiding 2004). One species, *P. leroyi*, Schouteden, 1955, has been described from Rwanda (Göllner-Scheiding 2004).

The genus *Plesionoma* can be recognised by the presence of 8–9 cephalic spines (or tubercles), the paranotum expanded in the posterior half into a prominent lobe, and the visible scent gland opening bearing the elevated peritreme forming an apically closed loop (Froeschner 1996).

P. capeneri differs from all other species of the genus in that the paranotum forms a triangular projection in its distal half (Fig. 1), the head armature is reduced to blunt tubercles shorter than the diameter of an eye, and the costal area is mostly composed of three rows of areoles. A different set of characters characterises other species.

Material examined: *Madagascar:* 2 exx., Toliara, Prov. Antafoky, elev. 60m, 23°28'45" S 44°3'58" E, 26 January 2002, Calif. Acad. of Sciences, Collectors: Frontier Project, gallery forest, leaf litter extraction, code: MGF001 (in the collection of Zoological Museum,

Humboldt University, Berlin, Germany). *Madagascar:* 1 ex. (Fig. 1), Tulear Province, Mikea Forest, NW of Manombo, el 30m, 22°54.22'S 43°28.53'E, 6–16 January 2002; Collector: R. Harin'Hala, California Acad. of Science, malaise trap – in deciduous dry forest, MA 02-18A-09 (in the collection of Zoological Museum, Humboldt University, Berlin, Germany).

Fig. 1. *Plesionoma capeneri*, dorsal view (photo B. Lis).

Note: All specimens from Madagascar have slightly smaller body dimensions (length: 3.22-3.54 mm, width: 1.58-1.64 mm). Moreover, the costal area and the paracosta are slightly narrower than in the South African specimens (Duarte Rodrigues 1998).

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